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Umesh Kumar

Department of Entomology,
Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel
University of Agriculture &
Technology, Meerut, Uttar
Pradesh, India

CS Prasad

Department of Entomology,
Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel
University of Agriculture &
Technology, Meerut, Uttar
Pradesh, India

Visvash Vaibhav

Department of Entomology,
Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel
University of Agriculture &
Technology, Meerut, Uttar
Pradesh, India

Visvash Vaibhav

Department of Entomology,
Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel
University of Agriculture &
Technology, Meerut, Uttar
Pradesh, India

Correspondence**Umesh Kumar**

Department of Entomology,
Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel
University of Agriculture &
Technology, Meerut, Uttar
Pradesh, India

Population dynamics of mango fruit fly species caught through methyl eugenol traps at different locations of Western plain zone of Uttar Pradesh

Umesh Kumar, CS Prasad, Visvash Vaibhav and Saty Saran

Abstract

Studies on population dynamics of different fruit flies, by using locally made methyl eugenol (ME) traps were conducted at two locations of Saharanpur district and Meerut district (U.P.) during January, 2013 to December, 2013. Throughout the year, four different species of fruit flies viz. *B. dorsalis*, *B. zonata*, *B. correcta* and *B. diversa* were identified by using methyl eugenol trap on mango orchards. The incidence of fruit flies was correlated with weather data. The maximum and minimum population of *B. dorsalis* was recorded in the months of August and January on mango orchard both at Saharanpur and Meerut District. Where, the maximum and minimum population of *B. zonata* was recorded in the months of July and January on mango orchard. The population of *B. diversa* and *B. correcta* were very low on mango orchard throughout the year. Only two species of fruit flies viz. *B. dorsalis* was dominant on mango orchard at both locations. The correlation coefficient between population and weather parameter in mango orchard both at Saharanpur and Meerut District showed highly positive correlation with maximum and minimum temperature, relative humidity and rainfall.

Keywords: methyl eugenol, *Bactrocera dorsalis*, *B. zonata*, *B. correcta*, *B. diversa*

Introduction

Fruit flies are one of the most important insect pests attacking mango and other fruits in India. Drew & Hancock (1994) [4] reported that fruit flies are mostly found on hosts such as mangoes and guavas, and in general seems likely to be polyphagous in nature. Fruit flies belong to the family Tephritidae of the order Diptera. The family Tephritidae is one of the largest families of insect order Diptera (Drew, 1989a) [3], comprising of predominantly medium sized, pictured-winged and highly ornamented flies commonly known as "fruit flies". India, nine i.e. *Bactrocera cucurbitae*, *B. dorsalis*, *B. zonata*, *B. tau*, *B. diversa*, *Dacus ciliates*, *Carpomyia vesuviana* (ber fly) and *Acanthiophilus helianthi* (seed fly) are identified to be the major and economically important (Madhura and Verghese, 2003) [10]. Parapheromones viz methyl eugenol is good male attractants and play an important role in management and monitoring of fruit flies. Sukla and Mishra (2005) [11] supported that hanging of traps baited with wooden blocks soaked in methyl eugenol, ethanol and malathion (6:4:1) @ 10 traps ha⁻¹ in mango orchards during fruiting period i.e. from April - August for the management of *B. diversa*, *B. dorsalis*, *B. zonata* and *B. correcta*.

Materials and Methods

The present studies were carried out at Saharanpur district and Meerut district (U.P.) during January, 2013 to December, 2013. The Rakshak Fruit Fly Trap recommended by Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA) Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India and supplied by Dr. Bala Saheb Sawant Konkan Agricultural University, Dapoli (Gujarat) was used. It is one liter plastic container with 100 mm base, 90 mm diameter top and 115 mm deep. It has a screw top lid with four entry holes of 25 mm in diameter evenly spaced 15 mm below the lip of the trap. A plastic chain is hooked in the centre on the upper side of screw top. On the lower side of the lid there is a hook for holding the wick/plywood. The lures were recharged fortnightly and were replaced at quarterly intervals in a year. As such, four traps were hung in mango orchard at 1.5 – 2.0 meter above from ground surface in shady condition to avoid sunlight and were located within the canopy of mango trees bearing fruits, approximately half the distance from the trunk to the outer edge of the foliage. The trapped flies were removed and counted every week starting from January, 2013 to December, 2013. Correlation between mean number of fruit flies and abiotic factors like mean maximum temperature, mean minimum temperature and relative humidity has been worked out.

Results and Discussion

The data presented in Table 1 indicates the fruit fly catches in different locations of Western plain zone of Uttar Pradesh. Four different species of fruit flies viz. *B. dorsalis*, *B. zonata*, *B. correcta* and *B. diversa* were identified by using methyl eugenol trap on mango orchards at both locations. (Saharanpur district) *B. dorsalis* was active and dominant during January to December among all of the trapped fruit flies species. Its maximum population recorded as 698 fruit flies /10 traps in the months of August. Results obtained in mango orchard, corroborate the findings of Bagle and Prasad (1983) ^[1], Suresh Babu and Viraktamath (2003) ^[9]. However,

Gupta and Bhatia (2000) ^[8] and Rajitha and Viraktamath (2006b) ^[13] reported a single peak of *B. dorsalis* during last week of August (30th standard week).

B. zonata was active throughout study period in the months of February to December. However maximum population was recorded in the months of October, 2013 with trap catches of 369 fruit flies/10 traps. Similar trend was also reported by Agarwal and Kumar (1999b) ^[6], Ravi Kumar (2005) ^[12]. Rajitha and Viraktamath (2006b) ^[13] reported two peaks during (October) 42nd and 45th standard weeks at Dharwad. Similar findings were also reported by Khalid Mahmood and Mishkatullah (2007) ^[14].

Table 1: Fruit fly catches at different locations of Saharanpur and Meerut district.

Months	Saharanpur district				Meerut district			
	Mango Fruit fly spp. trapped / 10 traps				Mango Fruit fly spp. trapped / 10 traps			
	<i>B. dorsalis</i>	<i>B. zonata</i>	<i>B. correcta</i>	<i>B. diversa</i>	<i>B. dorsalis</i>	<i>B. zonata</i>	<i>B. Correcta</i>	<i>B. diversa</i>
January	2	0	0	1	3	0	0	0
February	8	1	0	1	5	2	1	0
March	77	29	0	3	62	21	0	1
April	44	49	0	0	41	38	0	0
May	32	207	0	0	27	153	0	1
June	41	283	0	1	36	213	1	0
July	407	264	1	0	301	224	0	2
August	698	215	0	1	532	198	0	0
September	313	201	0	0	299	183	1	0
October	239	369	1	1	218	198	0	0
November	87	104	0	0	67	94	0	0
December	36	28	0	0	31	23	0	0

(Meerut district) *B. dorsalis* was active during January to December and it was dominant over all of these species. Its maximum population 532 fruit fly /10 trap in the months of August. Results obtained in mango orchard, corroborate the findings of Bagle and Prasad (1983) ^[1], Chiu and Chu (1986) ^[2], Verghese and Sudha Devi (1998) ^[6], However, Gupta and Bhatia (2000) ^[8] and Rajitha and Viraktamath (2006b) ^[13] reported a single peak of *B. dorsalis* during last week of August (30th standard week). Agarwal *et al.* (1999) ^[6] conducted fields studies on the annual population incidence of *B. dorsalis* showed peak occurrence during January-December 1986 using ME traps.

B. zonata was observed during in the months of July with the maximum population 224 fruit flies /10 trap. The population of fruit flies was low from January to April and varied between 2 to 38 flies/10 traps. Anjum *et al.* (2000) ^[7] reported peak population during the first week of July. Rajitha and Viraktamath (2006b) ^[13] reported four peaks during 42rd, 45th, 8th and 13th standard weeks at Dharwad.

References

1. Bagle BG, Prasad VG. Effect weather parameters on population dynamics of oriental fruit fly *Dacus dorsalis* Hendel. J Ent. Res. 1983; 7:95-98.
2. Chiu HT, Chu YI. The occurrence and injury of oriental fruit fly in the southern Taiwan. Plant Protection Bulletin, Taiwan. 1986; 28:313-321.
3. Drew RAI. The tropical fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) in Australian and oceanic region. Memoirs of Queensland Museum. 1989; 26:521.
4. Drew RAI, Hancock DL. The *Bactrocera dorsalis* complex of fruit flies in Asia. Bulletin of Entomological Research: Supplement Series. Supplement No. 2. CAB International, Wallingford, U.K, 1994.
5. Verghese A, Sudhadevi K. Relation between trap catch of *Bactrocera dorsalis* Hendel and abiotic factors. In: Proceedings of First National Symposium on Pest Management in Horticultural Crops, Bangalore, 1998, 15-18.
6. Agarwal ML, Kumar P. Effect of weather parameters on population dynamics of peach fruit fly, *B. zonata* (sounders). *Entomon.* 1999; 24(1):81-84.
7. Anjum S, Razaq M, Yazdani SS. Studies on seasonal activity and control of fruit flies (*Dacus* spp.) on mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) at Faisalabad Pakistan. *Arab J. Plant Prot.* 2000; 18:121-123.
8. Gupta D, Bhatia R. Population fluctuation of fruit flies, *Bactrocera* spp. in sub-mountainous mango and guava orchard. *Journal of Applied Horticulture.* 2000; 2(1):47-49.
9. Suresh Babu KS, Viraktamath S. Species diversity and population dynamics of fruit-flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) on mango in Northern Karnataka. *Pest Management and Economic Zoology.* 2003; 11(2):103- 110.
10. Madhura HS, Verghese A. Aguide to identification of some common fruit flies (*Bactrocera* species) (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Pest management in Horticulture ecosystem.* 2003; 10(1):1-10.
11. Shukla RP, Mishra AK. Controlling Insect Pest and Disease on mango. *India Horticulture.* 2005; 50(1):33-36.
12. Ravi Kumar CH. Studies on fruit flies in guava and mango orchrds with special reference to their management through mass trapping. M.Sc. (Ag.) thesis; University of Agricultural Sciences Dharwad, 2005, 90.
13. Rajitha AR, Viraktamath S. Investigations on the population dynamics of fruit flies in mango orchard at Dharwad. *Karnataka Journal of Agricultural Sciences.* 2006b; 19:134-137.
14. Khalid Mahmood Mishkatullah. Population dynamics of three species of genus *Bactrocera* (Diptera: Tephritidae: Dacinae) in BARI, Chakwal (Punjab), 2007.